

Comparison of Implementation of School Feeding Programmes in Public Primary Schools in Ondo and Osun States, Nigeria

*Adepoju, Adetokunboh Abayomi Ph.D.¹

Email: adecxyom@gmail.com

Tel: +2348032201379

Omotoyinbo, Oluwaseun Esther¹

Adebayo, Omolabake Wosilat²

¹Department of Primary Education, Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo, Nigeria

²Department of Home Economics, Adeyemi College of Education, Ondo, Nigeria

Abstract

The study compared if difference exists in the implementation of school feeding programmes between Ondo and Osun States, Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive research design. The population of the study consisted primary school teachers, head teachers, Local, Government Education Offices and parents. The samples of the study were made up of one hundred primary school teachers, two head teachers, two Local Government Education Offices and two parents. Data were analyzed using independent t-test statistical method. The findings showed that the school feeding programme is better implemented in Osun State than Ondo State. Also, there was no significant difference in the implementation in the two states. The study concluded that a myriad of challenges is confronting the programme and recommended that more funds should be provide, corrupt vendors be disengaged and proper monitoring should be put in place.

Keywords: Implementation, School Feeding, Challenges, Programme, Funds

Introduction

Nigerian is a developing country with poverty-stricken population who cannot afford three square meals, let alone financing education of their children (Ogunwole, 2016). The poor economic status of parents made it impossible for them to provide reading materials for their wards (Adepoju, 2018) and this is the reason for introducing free and compulsory primary education in Nigeria, National Policy on Education (NPE, 2014). Right from inception of Primary Education in Nigeria, proprietors and providers have been making frantic efforts to make it affordable to the entire citizenry because it is the foundation level upon which other levels are built. Igboanusi and Peter (2016), stated that if the foundation at the primary school is not well laid, pupils might not get it right in future. This accounts for the reason why governments, at all levels, leave no stone unturned and put incentives on ground to encourage pupils and parents so that the syndrome of out of school children will be reduced to its barest minimum. To achieve this, Lawani (2011), stressed that Primary Education was made free to beneficiaries when it was introduced by the missionaries. In the 19th century, the missionaries gave free books, slates and clothes (Adepoju & Olugboji 2020). Similarly, Ogbodo (1995), alluded that government dedicated 95% of allocation to education to Primary Education in 1955 when Universal Primary Education was introduced.

Reducing the number of out of school children, increasing enrolment and stabilising school children in the school environment have always been the cardinal factors for introducing motivational programmes to pupils and parents in public primary schools. The latest of these is the introduction of School Feeding Programme by the Federal Government in line with the provision of the National Policy on Education (NPE, 2014). According to the (NPE, 2014), School Feeding Programme is to ensure healthy development, retention and absorption of children in schools. Similarly in Kenya, school feeding programme is an economic bail out for indigent families to enrol their children in primary schools (Karaba, et al., 2019).

School Feeding Programme is a social package designed to provide food for hungry school children in order to safeguard their physical and mental well-being (Tijjani, et al., 2017). This study sees it as a planned policy that provides pupils with free meals provided daily by governments, communities or philanthropic organisations in schools. School feeding started as a philanthropic donour intervention in Europe in the 1700's, by 1900 Netherlands was the first nation to legislate it, it was officially introduced in the United Kingdom and the United States of America in 1930 and officially launched in Nigeria in September, 2005 under the supervision of the Federal Ministry of Education to alleviate hunger, increase enrolments in schools and boost students' performance (Adekunle & Christianah, 2016; Salifu, et al., 2018). The reason behind this programme was

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to reduce hunger and malnutrition among school children because according to Kiilu and Mugambi (2019), about eight hundred and forty two million (8,420,000) million people in the world have difficulties in getting food to eat; children are no exceptions in this regard. Corroborating this, Tijjani, et al., (2017) say sixty (60) million children go to school without food and a reasonable number of Nigerian children suffer from malnutrition because they lack important food nutrients such as vitamin A and iron. Similarly, Santrock (2014), remarks that malnutrition is inimical to all round development of children. The hazards inherent in malnutrition propelled governments and organisations to put in place School Feeding Programmes and the likes in different countries.

Poverty is a major cause of lateness to school (Adegunju, et al, 2019). To curtail this and other educational maladjustments, the study of Adekunle & Christianah (2016), reveals that School Feeding Programme, an initiative of MDG, was introduced to reduce hunger and malnutrition among school children. According to the scholars, meals given in schools, provide nutrients, boost punctuality and mental ability, reduces cost of funding by parents, and motivate parents to send their children to schools thereby increasing enrolment in schools as witnessed in Brazil, Philippine, Cambodia and Mali. Similarly, Kiilu & Mugambi, (2019) argue that school meals increase enrolment, attendance, academic performance and reduce rate of drop out. School feeding is divided into two, namely, in-school feeding and take home. The in-school food is served hot/warm while the take home is cooked at home as found out by these scholars. Home Grown School Feeding Programme provides employments for local farmers and food vendors employed to cook under the supervision of government officials (Adekunle & Christianah, 2016). Yardsticks for effective School Feeding Programme include policy formulation, proper implementation, funding and competent personnel (Kiilu & Mugambi, 2019).

Nutritional programmes are put in place by government to improve food security, prevention of malnutrition and reduction of poverty among children (Ogunwole, 2016). If nourishment is to be ensured, the quality and the quantity of food served should be good and adequate. Poor nutrition in children leads to health challenges such a Marasmus and Kwashiorkor which result in loss of body weight and swollen abdomen/feet respectively and that is why a body called Women, Infants and Children (WIN) programme in United States of America provides funds for the supply of nutritious meals to children from low-income homes (Santrock, 2014).

Food is any liquid or solid substance eaten by man for essential nourishment, reproduction, building/repair of worn-out body cells, respiration, supply of energy and body growth (Soyinbo, et al., 1997; Ogunwole, 2016). Foods are grouped according to their sources, that is, vegetarian and non-vegetarian (Sasikala & Chanchalor, 2016), according to the nutrients they supply and according to the functions they perform in the body system (Ukeagbu, et al., 2014 and Micheal, 2018). These classifications are hereby presented in this study in these tabular forms:

Table 1: Classifications According to Sources

S/N	Classes	Sources
A	Vegetarian	Vegetables, fruits, roots, tubers
B	Non-vegetarian	Eggs, meat, fish,

Table 2: Classifications According to Nutrients

S/N	Classes	Sources
A	Vitamins	Vegetables, eggs, milk etc
B	Mineral salts	Vegetables, fruits
C	Carbohydrate	Yam, bread, rice etc
D	Fats	Butter, palm oil, groundnut etc
E	Proteins	Egg, fish, meat
F	Water	Beverages, mineral water, beer

Table 3: Classifications According to Functions

S/N	Classes	Functions
A	Carbohydrate and fats	Energy giver/suppliers
B	Proteins	Body builders
C	Vitamins, mineral salts and water	Protections, mobility
D	Roughages	Regulation, prevention

The functions of these classes of food are interwoven in the sense that some body building foods such as eggs and milk are also rich in vitamins and mineral salts (Ukeagbu et al, 2014). Food should not only be taken, balanced diet should also

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be ensured in the meals eaten to avoid malnutrition in children. Oladele (1999), defines balanced diet as meal that contains the right proportion of nutrients for effective maintenance of the body. It is against this background that Sasikala & Chanchalor (2016), comment that poor nutrition makes the body system vulnerable to diseases.

Like other educational programmes, school feeding is bedevilled with a myriad of problems, such as lack of correlation between its funding and its manifestation and corruption (Salifu, et al., 2018). Similarly, in Kenya, the study of Kiilu & Mugambi (2019), reveal that in the community where the study was carried out, the community shoulders the responsibility of school feeding programme which implies that government does not show mush commitment to the programme. Also, in Kenya, school feeding programme suffers financial crises (Karaba, et al, 2019).

Studies before this left a gap that this study sought to fill. The study of Sasikala & Chanchalor (2016), examined the nutritional status of school boys and girls in a school in India. The study conducted by Adekunle & Christianah (2016) and Tijjani, et al (2017), looked at the effects of School Feeding Programmes on enrolment, retention and academic performance in Osun State and Maiduguri, Nigeria and the work of Kiilu & Mugambi (2019) considered the level of implementation and the programme sponsors in an area in Kenya. This study sought to compare the implementation of School Feeding Programmes in Ondo and Osun States, Nigeria with a view to determining the similarities and differences.

The study relied on behaviourism as its theoretical base because the theory has a direct correlation with this study. Behaviourism focuses on observable behaviours that are responses to stimuli in the learning environment (Bakare, 2015). Experiments by behaviourists yielded two types of conditionings, namely, classical and operant conditionings. Classical conditioning, propounded and ventilated by Ivan Pavlov, is Stimulus-Response theory that theorises that learners naturally response to stimulus when provided through his experiment that which showed that dogs salivate when they see food (unconditioned stimulus) when they hear sound of a bell (conditioned stimulus) (Tella, et al., 1990). Operant conditioning, propounded by B.F Skinner and ventilated by Edward Thorndike, hypothesises that when a response to a stimulus is rewarded, that behaviour will be repeated (Adedayo & Dunapo, 2016). Expatiating further on this, Cruikshank, Jenkins, & Metcalf (2009), comment that operant conditioning is learning by reinforcement when an action is rewarded, it will be rewarded but when not rewarded, there is the likelihood of it not being repeated. Food served (stimulus) motivates pupils to come to school regularly and punctually (response) since their coming is rewarded.

School feeding programme was introduced to cater for the nutritional needs of pupils and discourage out of school child syndrome. This makes the Federal Government to budget for it annually and implement it through various state governments. At inception, one meal was given to each child daily, which served as mid-day meal, that is, brunch that attracted and retained pupils in schools. Unfortunately, in one of the studies conducted by the researcher, it was observed that in some primary schools meals were not being served, in some it is epileptic and in some primary schools only certain grades are being fed. To add insult to the injury, the quality and quantity of food served is worrisome. Government only awards the contracts to contactors who are not forth coming and execute shady jobs. Head teachers are not even in control of the caterers assigned to their schools. It was as a result of this that this study set out to examine the implementation of the school feeding programme in Ondo and Osun States of Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of the study was to compare the implementation of school feeding programmes in primary schools in Ondo and Osun States. In doing this the following were the objectives of the study.

1. To assess the extent of implementation of school feeding programme in Ondo and Osun States
2. To assess the quality of food served to primary school pupils in Ondo and Osun States; and
3. To determine the effects of school feeding programme in Ondo and Osun Sates.

Questions

To get this done, the study raised the following research questions in line with the objectives to guide the study.

1. What is the extent of implementation of school feeding programme in Ondo and Osun States?
2. What is the quality of food served to primary school pupils?
3. To what extent does school feeding programme impact on primary school pupils in Ondo and Osun States?

Hypothesis

One research hypothesis was also formulated for this study as thus:

There is no significant difference between implementation of school feeding programmes in Ondo and Osun States.

Methodology

The study used mixed method approach because numerical and non-numerical data were needed for the study and for data method triangulation to achieve accuracy in the study. The design was a descriptive survey of two selected local government areas in Ondo and Osun States of Nigeria. The population of the study were primary school teachers, head teachers, local government education officials and parents. To obtain quantitative data one hundred primary school teachers were randomly selected while two head teachers, two Local Government Education Authority Officials and two literate parents were purposively selected to obtain qualitative data from the states making one hundred and six samples. Two research instruments were designed for this study, namely, a fifteen item structured 4 point likert scale questionnaire was used to obtain responses from teachers and a five item semi-structured questions completed by head teachers, Local Government Education Authority Officials and the literate parents. The time of the study fell within the COVID 19 pandemic which restricted the movement of people and this necessitated the researcher to mail the research instruments to academic colleagues, herein in this study referred to as research assistants, whose places of abode were in the areas chosen for the study. The research assistants personally administered the instruments on the one hundred and six samples, collated the data and mailed them to the researcher.

The validity of structured questionnaire was ensured by giving the draft to research experts who made necessary corrections and adjustments to determine face validity, content validity and construct validity while the semi-structured questions were made error free through thorough proof reading. Linkert ranking scale and T-test were used for quantitative data analysis while thematic analysis was used for qualitative data. To establish credibility of study, data triangulation, anonymity and confirmability were employed. Thus Participant A, Participant, Participant C Participant D, Participant E and Participant F were used to label the participants

Results

Research Question 1

What is the extent of implementation of school feeding programme in Ondo and Osun States?

Table 4: Implementation of School Feeding Programme in Ondo State

S/N	Item:	Very often	Often	Rare	Very rare	X	SD
1	School meals are provided everyday.	5	10	24	11	2.18	5.358
2	Enough foods are given to pupils.	4	5	13	28	1.7	4.725
3	Government monitors school feeding programmes.	6	17	18	9	2.4	5.388
4	Government finances school feeding programme.	19	20	7	4	3.02	7.85
5	All school benefit from school feeding programme.	3	13	7	27	1.84	4.900
Total		37	65	69	79	2.23	5.430

Table 4 shows that the calculated mean (X) of 2.23 is less than the cut off mean (X) of 2.50. This implies that school feeding programme is not well implemented in Ondo State. For this table, the standard deviation is 5.430

Table 5: Implementation School Feeding Programme in Osun State

S/N	Item:	Very often	Often	Rare	Very rare	X	SD
1	School meals are provided everyday.	32	18	0	0	3.64	9.39
2	Enough foods are given to pupils.	34	14	2	0	3.64	9.55
3	Government monitors school feeding programmes.	38	12	0	0	3.76	10.64

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4	Government finances school feeding programme.	46	4	0	0	3.92	12.44
5	All school benefit from school feeding programme.	20	20	4	6	3.08	6.47
Total						3.61	48.49

On Table 5, the calculated mean (\bar{X}) of 3.61 is greater than the cut off mean (\bar{X}) of 2.50. This implies that School Feeding Programme is well implemented in Osun State. On this table, the standard deviation is 48.49

Research Question 2

What is the quality of food served to primary school pupils?

Table 6: Quality and Quantity of food provided in Ondo State

S/N	Item:	Very often	Often	Rare	Very rare	X
1	Foods served include eggs, milk and meat	2	18	13	17	2.36
2	Provision of food such as yam, bread and rice	4	8	24	14	2.04
3	Provision of food such as butter, palm oil and vegetable oil	13	2	9	26	2.04
4	Inclusion of vegetables and fruits.	1	6	23	20	1.76
5	Water and juice are served	1	1	8	40	1.26
Total		21	35	77	117	1.84

As shown on Table 6, the calculated mean (\bar{X}) of 1.84 is less than the cut off mean (\bar{X}) of 2.50. The implication is that food served in Ondo State in the School Feeding Programme is poor in terms of quality and quantity.

Table 7: Quality and Quantity of food provided in Osun State

S/N	Item:	Very often	Often	Rare	Very rare	X
1	Foods served include eggs, milk and meat	40	10	0	0	3.8
2	Provision of food such as yam, bread and rice	35	10	5	0	3.5
3	Provision of food such as butter, palm oil and vegetable oil	32	8	10	0	3.44
4	Inclusion of vegetables and fruits.	40	10	0	0	3.8
5	Water and juice are served	42	8	0	0	3.84
Total						3.68

Table 7 shows that the calculated mean (\bar{X}) of 3.68 is greater than the cut off mean (\bar{X}) of 2.50. This implies that food provided in School Feeding Programme in Osun State is good in terms of quality and quantity.

Research Question 3

To what extent does school feeding programme impact on primary school pupils in Ondo and Osun States?

Table 8: Impacts of School Feeding Programme in Ondo State

S/N	Item:	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Disagree Strongly	X
1	School meals encourage parents to send their children to school.	19	19	12	0	3.38
2	Pupils stay in schools because of the meals served.	19	20	10	1	3.14

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3	School meals enhance academic performance.	10	30	10	0	3.0
4	School meals make pupils to be punctual in schools	21	19	7	3	3.1
5	School meals reduce malnutrition among pupils.	12	31	4	3	3.04
Total		81	119	43	7	3.92

The calculated mean (X) of 3.92 on Table 8 is greater than the cut off mean (X) of 2.50. This implies that the respondents agreed that School Feeding Programme in Ondo State is beneficial to the pupils.

Table 9: Benefits of School Feeding Programme in Osun State

S/N	Item:	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Disagree Strongly	X
1	School meals encourage parents to send their children to school.	40	10	0	0	3.8
2	Pupils stay in schools because of the meals served.	38	6	6	0	3.64
3	School meals enhance academic performance.	28	22	0	0	3.76
4	School meals make pupils to be punctual in schools	44	6	0	0	3.88
5	School meals reduce malnutrition among pupils.	42	4	4	0	3.76
Total		192	48	10	0	3.77

Table 9 shows that the calculated mean (X) of 3.77 is greater than the cut off mean (X) of 2.50. Therefore, the respondents agreed that pupils benefit immensely from school feeding programme in Osun State.

Hypothesis (Ho)

There is no significant difference between implementation of school feeding programmes in Ondo and Osun States.

Table 10: t-test analysis of the implementation of school feeding programmes in Ondo and Osun States

States	N	X	SD	Df	t-cal.	t-critical	Decision
Ondo	50	2.23	5.43	98	0.85	1.96	Not significant
Osun		3.61	9.70				

Table 10 shows that t-calculated of 0.85 is less than t-critical of 1.96, hence, the hypothesis is retained. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the implementation of School Feeding Programmes in Ondo and Osun states.

Discussion of Findings

Though the respondents agreed that school feeding is helpful to pupils in Ondo State, according to Table E, which shows that the calculated mean (X) of 3.92 is greater than the cut-off mean (X) of 2.50. This is in line with Kiilu and Mugambi (2019) who opined that school feeding increases enrolment, attendance and boost performance, Table A above shows that school feeding programme is not well implemented in Ondo state since the calculated mean (X) 2.23 is less than the cut-off mean (X) of 2.50 which corroborates the situation in Kenya where the programme suffers neglect (Karaba, et al., 2019) and the quality of food served is very poor because the food lacked basic nutrients which make pupils vulnerable to diseases (Sasikala & Chanchalor, 2016) and also confirms the views of Tijjani, et al., (2017) and Santrock (2014) who remarked that Nigerian children are undernourished because they lack food nutrients which is dangerous to their well-being.

Table 5 shows that school feeding is well implemented in Osun State as indicated by the calculated mean (X) of 3.61 which is greater than the cut-off mean (X) of 2.50. This enhances enrolment, attendance and performance in schools (Adekunle and Christianah, 2016). The respondents also agreed that school feeding is beneficial to pupils as indicated by the calculated mean (X) of 3.77 which is greater than the cut-off mean of 2.50. Food served in the State are of good quality because as they contain

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vital nutrients for proper maintenance of the body (Oladele, 1999). This is indicated by the calculated mean (X) of 3.37 which is greater than the cut-off mean (X) of 2.50. In a nutshell, Table G shows that t-calculated of 0.85 is less than t-critical of 1.96, hence, the research hypothesis, 'There is no significant difference between implementation of school feeding programmes in Ondo and Osun States' is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the implementation of school feeding programmes in Ondo and Osun states.

From the qualitative data collected in this study, the following themes were derived and discussed: Findings show that the Federal Government of Nigeria, the state governments and the United Nations are the major sponsors of the programme in both states. All the participants attested to this claim in their responses. For examples, Participant B said, 'Federal Government in conjunction with state counterpart fund.' while Participant E said, 'United Nations is responsible jointly funding by the Federal Government of Nigeria. This finding aligns with the views of Adekunle and Christianah, (2016) and Salifu, et al, (2018) who remarked that government in different countries provide meals for school children.

School Feeding Programme is of immense benefits to school children in the two states under this study. These benefits include but not limited punctuality and regularity in school, enhanced academic performance, increase in enrolment and nourishment of the school children. The responses of the participants to question 3 above are indicators of this. Though Participant C said, 'It has no effects because the food is too small.' other participants remarked that the programme nourishes the pupils, boosts enrolment, prevents ailments/diseases and increase their academic performance. This finding confirms the studies of Adekunle and Christianah (2016) and Kiilu and Mugambi (2019), who revealed that school feeding programme, among others, encourages enrolment, attendance, punctuality, academic performance and spared the parents the burden of feeding their wards.

The participants confirmed the view of (Salifu, et al., 2018) who lamented shambolic implementation of school feeding programme. The comment of these two participants to question four (4): What are the constraints against school feeding programme in your area?, revealed this pathetic situation. Participant E: Very numerous: Irregularity in the funding, Lack of experienced stewards, distances from home, high prices of food stuffs. Participant A: Bad roads. Delay in finance. Unfaithfulness. There was a vendor who packed remnant from a party and took it to a school to feed the pupils. There were many cases in which the vendors would collect money and not supply the pupils with food meant for them. These responses expose the corrupt practices associated with the programme and the health implication on school children who are served left over food by unscrupulous vendors.

Conclusion

The study shows that school feeding programme is bedevilled with some challenges, most especially in Ondo State where the quality, spread and finance are poor. Lack of monitoring also affects the programme. This noble project should not be handled with levity so that its aims and objectives will not be defeated.

Recommendations

Based on the above awful findings, the study hereby makes the following recommendations so that this befitting educational programme will not be a white elephant's project:

1. More funds should be allocated to cushion the effect of shortage of funds;
2. Corrupt vendors should be relieved of their positions to guide against poor quality and quantity of food served to pupils;
3. The programme should be well monitored to see that its implementation is well spread most especially in Ondo State;
4. The quality and quantity of food prepared should be screened by nutritionists, most especially in Ondo State to prevent health hazards.

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